

Functions of ubiquitin and SUMO in DNA replication and replication stress

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2 **Néstor García-Rodríguez^{1,2}, Ronald P. Wong^{1,2}, Helle D. Ulrich^{1*}**

3 ¹ Institute of Molecular Biology, Ackermannweg 4, D 55128 Mainz, Germany

4 ² Equal contribution

5 * **Correspondence:** Helle D. Ulrich, Institute of Molecular Biology, Ackermannweg 4, D 55128
6 Mainz, Germany.

7 h.ulrich@imb-mainz.de

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10

11 **Abstract**

12 Complete and faithful duplication of its entire genetic material is one of the essential prerequisites for
13 a proliferating cell to maintain genome stability. Yet, during replication DNA is particularly
14 vulnerable to insults. On the one hand, lesions in replicating DNA frequently cause a stalling of the
15 replication machinery, as most DNA polymerases cannot cope with defective templates. This
16 situation is aggravated by the fact that strand separation in preparation for DNA synthesis prevents
17 common repair mechanisms relying on strand complementarity, such as base and nucleotide excision
18 repair, from working properly. On the other hand, the replication process itself subjects the DNA to a
19 series of hazardous transformations, ranging from the exposure of single-stranded DNA to
20 topological contortions and the generation of nicks and fragments, which all bear the risk of inducing
21 genomic instability. Dealing with these problems requires rapid and flexible responses, for which
22 posttranslational protein modifications that act independently of protein synthesis are particularly
23 well suited. Hence, it is not surprising that members of the ubiquitin family, particularly ubiquitin
24 itself and SUMO, feature prominently in controlling many of the defensive and restorative measures
25 involved in the protection of DNA during replication. In this review we will discuss the contributions
26 of ubiquitin and SUMO to genome maintenance specifically as they relate to DNA replication. We
27 will consider cases where the modifiers act during regular, i.e. unperturbed stages of replication, such
28 as initiation, fork progression and termination, but also give an account of their functions in dealing
29 with lesions, replication stalling and fork collapse.

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31

32 **1 Introduction**

33 DNA replication in eukaryotes is a multi-step process that is tightly coupled to both cell cycle
34 progression and the DNA damage response (Leman and Noguchi, 2013; Siddiqui et al., 2013; Berti
35 and Vindigni, 2016). After completion of mitosis during the G1 stage of the cell cycle, replication
36 origins are prepared for activation in a process called origin licensing (Siddiqui et al., 2013). This
37 reaction results in the formation of pre-replicative complexes (pre-RCs) at replication origins, which
38 include key components of the replicative helicase, albeit in an inactive form. Licensing restricts
39 origin firing to once per cell cycle, thus preventing genome instability induced by re-replication. At
40 the entry into S phase, DNA replication is initiated by the action of cell cycle-regulated kinases,
41 resulting in the activation of the replicative helicase and the separation of strands to form the first
42 replication forks. This is accompanied by the assembly of replisomes, multi-protein complexes that
43 comprise not only the helicase and several DNA polymerases, but also a large number of accessory
44 factors responsible for monitoring replication fork progression, generating checkpoint and damage
45 signals, and coordination of DNA synthesis with chromatin assembly (Leman and Noguchi, 2013). In
46 eukaryotes, origin firing follows a temporally regulated program throughout S phase, giving rise to
47 distinct early- and late-replicating regions of the genome (Renard-Guillet et al., 2014). The pattern of
48 origin firing is flexible and reacts to situations such as the stalling of individual forks or the
49 perception of a global damage signal by the cell. DNA synthesis proceeds bi-directionally, initiated
50 by the deposition of short RNA primers that are subsequently extended by DNA polymerase α .
51 Leading and lagging strand replication by the main replicative DNA polymerases ϵ and δ ,
52 respectively, is closely coordinated with the unwinding of the template DNA. As a consequence,
53 accumulation of extended regions of single-stranded (ss)DNA is perceived as a sign of fork stalling
54 and triggers a checkpoint response that suppresses the firing of late replication origins and prevents
55 entry into mitosis (Leman and Noguchi, 2013). The nicks in the emerging lagging strand, arising
56 from its discontinuous synthesis, are successively sealed by DNA ligase. As replication units
57 (replicons) from neighboring origins meet, replication forks merge and replication is terminated by
58 the disassembly of the replisomes. Since DNA replication takes place in the context of chromatin,
59 removal of nucleosomes in front of the helicase and their renewed deposition after passage of the
60 replication fork need to be synchronized with DNA synthesis (Groth, 2009). This coordination,
61 actively mediated by components of the replisome, also protects against the loss of epigenetic marks
62 during replication.

63 Accurate control over all stages of DNA replication is of vital importance for the maintenance of
64 genome integrity in proliferating cells. Both incomplete replication and over-replication interfere
65 with proper chromosome segregation, and defects in replication fidelity pose a serious threat to
66 genome stability due to an increased mutation load. Hence, the mechanisms ensuring complete and
67 accurate replication need to be considered as part of a cell's repertoire to defend itself against insults
68 to its genome. By reversibly altering the properties of their target proteins, various different
69 posttranslational protein modifications contribute significantly to these processes. Over the past
70 decade, we have witnessed the emergence of ubiquitin and SUMO as key regulators of genome
71 maintenance pathways (Ulrich and Walden, 2010; Jackson and Durocher, 2013). Although best
72 known for mediating protein degradation, ubiquitin can convey a variety of non-proteolytic signals.
73 This can partly be ascribed to the effects of mono-ubiquitylation, but also to ubiquitin's ability to
74 form polymeric chains of different geometries, recognized by highly chain-selective effector proteins
75 (Komander and Rape, 2012). More recently, it has been realized that SUMO can also trigger
76 degradation of its targets by forming polymeric SUMO chains interacting with a class of enzymes
77 known as SUMO-targeted ubiquitin ligases (STUbLs) (Prudden et al., 2007; Sriramachandran and

78 Dohmen, 2014). Hence, both proteolytic and non-proteolytic contributions need to be considered in
79 discussing the effects of ubiquitin and SUMO on DNA replication.

80 This review will cover the functions of ubiquitin and SUMO during unperturbed replication, i.e.
81 during origin licensing, replication elongation and termination, and with regard to chromatin
82 assembly and nuclear structure. Another important aspect will be the response to replication stress.
83 Naturally, this topic overlaps to some degree with other chapters in this volume, such as those on
84 chromatin reorganization (Greenberg), translesion synthesis (Sabbioneda), the Fanconi anemia
85 pathway (Huang) and double-strand break (DSB)-induced damage signaling (Mailand), to which we
86 will refer where appropriate. Also, as much of the recent progress in the field can be ascribed to
87 large-scale siRNA screens and proteomic approaches, mechanistic information is often lagging
88 behind the identification of novel modification targets and conjugation factors. We will therefore
89 refrain from giving a comprehensive account of all the enzymes and substrates involved in DNA
90 replication and focus on representative examples where a relevant functional context is available.

91 **2 Replication of intact DNA**

92 The function of ubiquitylation in unperturbed DNA replication has been the subject of an excellent
93 recent review (Moreno and Gambus, 2015), to which the reader is referred for details, particularly
94 with respect to proteolytic functions of ubiquitylation. Here we complement this with information on
95 the roles of protein SUMOylation, and we discuss the recurring problem of distinguishing
96 modifications that are inherently part of the replication process from those occurring in response to
97 spontaneous problems based on difficult-to-replicate sequences or chromatin regions.

98 **2.1 Contributions of ubiquitin and SUMO to origin licensing and replication initiation**

99 At the entry into S phase, ubiquitin functions predominantly as an inducer of proteasomal
100 degradation, owing to its prominent role in cell cycle regulation (Teixeira and Reed, 2013).
101 Preparation for DNA replication requires loading of the hexameric ring-shaped Mcm2-7 complex
102 onto origins of replication, mediated by the origin recognition complex (ORC) and two auxiliary
103 factors, Cdt1 and Cdc6 (Siddiqui et al., 2013). Establishment of the pre-RC can only proceed late in
104 mitosis and during G1 phase, when cyclin-dependent kinase (CDK) levels are low. This is achieved
105 by a large, multi-subunit ubiquitin ligase, the anaphase promoting complex (APC/C), which induces
106 degradation of mitotic cyclins and of the CDK-activating phosphatase Cdc25 (King et al.,
107 1995;Donzelli et al., 2002;Teixeira and Reed, 2013). In vertebrates, the APC/C also targets the Cdt1
108 inhibitor geminin for degradation (McGarry and Kirschner, 1998).

109 In order to initiate S phase, two helicase coactivators – Cdc45 and the GINS complex – are recruited
110 to pre-RCs, assembling the active replicative helicase, the CMG complex (Cdc45-Mcm2-7-GINS).
111 Once the initial unwinding occurs, DNA polymerases and the sliding clamp, PCNA, are recruited to
112 assemble the replisome and establish the replication fork (Leman and Noguchi, 2013). Origin firing
113 requires a rise in CDK activity. Accordingly, APC/C activity is downregulated, mainly by inhibition
114 of its regulatory subunit Cdh1 (Eldridge et al., 2006;Fukushima et al., 2013;Lau et al., 2013), but also
115 by autoubiquitylation and degradation of its cognate ubiquitin conjugating enzyme (E2), UbcH10, a
116 process induced in the absence of APC/C substrates (Rape and Kirschner, 2004). This allows an
117 accumulation of G1-specific cyclins. Additionally, CDK inhibitors, such as p27 and p21, are
118 degraded (Starostina and Kipreos, 2012). Three different E3s, KPC, Pirh2 and the Skp1-Cullin-F-box
119 complex SCF^{Skp2}, are known to act on p27 in a temporally and spatially ordered fashion during G1
120 and early S phase. The p21 protein is also a substrate of SCF^{Skp2}, but in addition, this factor is

121 targeted by an intriguing mechanism that directly couples ubiquitylation to S phase entry (Abbas et
122 al., 2008; Kim et al., 2008). The cognate E3, Cullin-RING ligase CRL4^{Cdt2}, recognizes its substrate
123 only in conjunction with the replication clamp, PCNA, and only when PCNA is encircling DNA. The
124 relevant degradation signal, which includes a PCNA-interacting peptide (PIP), is also found in other
125 factors whose removal is associated with S phase, such as the fission yeast inhibitor of ribonucleotide
126 reductase, Spd1, and the G1-specific transcription factor E2F1 from *Drosophila melanogaster*.
127 (Havens and Walter, 2011; Ulrich, 2014) Thus, by coupling substrate recognition to binding of loaded
128 PCNA, CRL4^{Cdt2} is able to read the state of the replication machinery as an activating signal.

129 Firing of origins needs to be strictly limited to once per cell cycle to avoid problems of re-replication.
130 This is achieved through a process known as origin licensing that restricts pre-RC assembly to G1
131 (Moreno and Gambus, 2015). In order to render the process irreversible, essential loading factors,
132 such as Cdt1 and Cdc6, are eliminated when cells enter S phase. In many organisms, this is again
133 mediated by ubiquitin-mediated proteolysis. Human Cdt1 is ubiquitylated by at least two different
134 E3s of the CRL family, SCF^{Skp2} and – as described above – CRL4^{Cdt2} (Li et al., 2003; Zhong et al.,
135 2003). Cdc6 is deactivated either by export from the nucleus or by degradation following its
136 ubiquitylation by CRL4^{Cdt2} (Saha et al., 1998; Clijsters and Wolthuis, 2014). In budding yeast,
137 SCF^{Cdc4} mediates ubiquitylation of Cdc6 (Drury et al., 1997).

138 In contrast to the pervasive influence of ubiquitin, SUMO appears to exert more subtle regulatory
139 effects on replication initiation. In a cell-free system based on *Xenopus laevis* egg extracts, inhibition
140 of SUMOylation was found to increase replication rates by allowing a larger number of origins to fire
141 (Bonne-Andrea et al., 2013). The negative effect of SUMO on origin firing was attributable to the
142 modification of cyclin E following recruitment of the cyclin E-CDK complex to pre-RCs. The notion
143 that most cells only use a sub-set of their potential origins in each S phase suggests that SUMO may
144 in this context contribute to limiting excessive origin firing. In the budding yeast, Wei and Zhao
145 recently reported an apparently unrelated phenomenon that likewise suggests a negative impact of
146 SUMO on origin firing (Wei and Zhao, 2016). They observed a cell-cycle regulated SUMOylation of
147 Mcm2-7, peaking at the pre-RC stage when the complex is loaded onto origins, but declining upon
148 origin firing at the G1-to-S transition. Artificial enhancement of local SUMOylation inhibited CMG
149 assembly and origin firing, most likely by means of recruiting a phosphatase that prevented essential
150 phosphorylation events required for CMG activation. Intriguingly, both SUMOylation and
151 deSUMOylation of Mcm proteins are accomplished by multiple E3s and isopeptidases in a subunit-
152 specific manner, and significant differences were noted in the cell cycle regulation of individual Mcm
153 subunits (de Albuquerque et al., 2016). Moreover, it is important to note that other components of
154 pre-RCs have also been identified as SUMOylation targets, among them the subunits of ORC
155 (Golebiowski et al., 2009). Hence, it remains to be established whether the negative effect of SUMO
156 on origin firing observed in this study is due to the modification of an individual Mcm subunit, the
157 Mcm2-7 complex in its entirety, or a general accumulation of SUMO around the pre-RC.

158 2.2 Proteomic analyses of replicating chromatin

159 A wealth of information has emerged from the isolation of chromatin-associated proteins from
160 proliferating cells, followed by mass spectrometry. Proteome-wide analyses identified numerous
161 replication factors as ubiquitylation targets in human cells, including integral components of the
162 replisome such as GINS and the Mcm2-7 helicase complex, the Replication Factor C (RFC) clamp
163 loader complex, as well as all the replicative DNA polymerases and many associated factors (Wagner
164 et al., 2011). Comparison of substrate spectra in the absence and presence of the proteasome inhibitor
165 MG132 revealed both proteolytic and non-proteolytic roles of ubiquitylation. Similarly, a systematic

166 screen in the budding yeast *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* identified a significant number of replisome
167 components targeted by SUMO, including components of the Mcm2-7 complex, subunits of DNA
168 polymerases and the RFC complex, the Rad27 flap endonuclease and topoisomerases Top1 and Top2
169 (Cremona et al., 2012). A recent study, using a procedure to isolate proteins on nascent DNA
170 (iPOND) followed by mass spectrometry, characterized proteins enriched in the proximity of
171 replisomes in an unprecedented spatial resolution. Interestingly, SUMOylation was predominant on
172 factors near the replisome, while ubiquitylated proteins prevailed on mature chromatin (Lopez-
173 Contreras et al., 2013). Although the implications of this distribution are not well understood, an
174 appropriate balance appears to be important for replication and genome stability, as the ubiquitin
175 isopeptidase USP7 was found to be responsible for maintaining SUMOylated proteins at replication
176 forks by means of protecting them from ubiquitylation (Lecona et al., 2016). USP7 activity was
177 found essential for origin firing as well as replisome progression, and intriguingly, one of its
178 functions appears to be the deubiquitylation of SUMO itself.

179 Despite these observations, the functions of most replisome-associated modifications remain to be
180 explored, and the notion that many of the SUMOylation events were found to be enriched after
181 exposure of the cells to DNA damage (Cremona et al., 2012) raises the question of whether these
182 modifications are inherent in the replication process or represent a response to spontaneous
183 replication problems or low-level DNA damage.

184 **2.3 PCNA modifications during unperturbed DNA replication**

185 Posttranslational modifications heavily modulate the function of the eukaryotic sliding clamp. PCNA
186 is a homotrimeric, ring-shaped complex that encircles DNA and functions as a processivity factor for
187 DNA polymerases. In addition, PCNA serves as an interaction platform for numerous factors
188 involved in DNA replication, repair, chromatin dynamics, cohesion and cell cycle regulation
189 (Moldovan et al., 2007;Ulrich and Takahashi, 2013).

190 During unperturbed replication, budding yeast PCNA is modified by SUMO at a highly conserved
191 lysine, K164, and to a minor extent at K127 (Hoege et al., 2002) (Figure 1A). Modification at K164
192 is mediated by the SUMO E2 Ubc9 in combination with the SUMO E3 Siz1 and is triggered by
193 loading of the clamp onto DNA (Parker et al., 2008). SUMOylation at K127 *in vivo* requires Siz2
194 (Parker et al., 2008). The modification enhances interaction with an antirecombinogenic helicase,
195 Srs2, at replication forks. Srs2 interacts with PCNA^{SUMO} via its carboxy-terminal tail containing a
196 PIP-like PCNA interaction motif adjacent to a canonical SUMO interacting motif (SIM) (Pfander et
197 al., 2005;Armstrong et al., 2012). Recruitment of Srs2 prevents unwanted homologous recombination
198 (HR) by disrupting Rad51 filaments (Krejci et al., 2003;Veaute et al., 2003;Papouli et al.,
199 2005;Pfander et al., 2005). In addition, the presence of SUMO on PCNA boosts the damage-induced
200 activity of the ubiquitin ligase Rad18 towards PCNA, again through a SIM in the E3 sequence
201 (Parker and Ulrich, 2012). As a consequence, upon encounter of replication-stalling DNA lesions,
202 damage processing is channeled into a bypass pathway that depends on PCNA ubiquitylation (Figure
203 1B, and see below). Hence, PCNA SUMOylation appears to function as a pre-emptive defense
204 measure to influence pathway choice in response to replication stress. The modification also appears
205 to enhance interaction with an alternative clamp loader complex, RLC-Elg1, which has been
206 proposed to mediate PCNA unloading during replication (Parnas et al., 2010;Kubota et al., 2013).
207 However, SUMOylation is not essential for Elg1 action on PCNA.

208 SUMOylation at K164 has been observed not only in budding yeast, but also in *Xenopus laevis* egg
209 extracts, chicken DT40 cells and, more recently, in mammalian cells (Leach and Michael,

210 2005;Arakawa et al., 2006;Gali et al., 2012;Moldovan et al., 2012). In human cells, expression of a
211 PCNA-SUMO fusion protein inhibits spontaneous as well as damage-induced HR (Gali et al., 2012).
212 Furthermore, a novel PCNA-interacting factor, the helicase PARI, has been suggested to function
213 analogously to Srs2 in humans: it contains PIP and SIM motifs for interaction with PCNA^{SUMO} and
214 suppresses HR by removing Rad51 from DNA (Moldovan et al., 2012). However, SUMOylated
215 PCNA is present at very low levels in mammalian when compared to yeast cells, and its detection
216 requires overexpression of epitope-tagged SUMO alleles (Gali et al., 2012). Whether this reflects the
217 need for a tighter regulation of the process in the yeast system with its naturally higher rate of
218 recombination remains to be explored.

219 In response to DNA damage, PCNA is mono- and polyubiquitylated at K164 (Hoegge et al., 2002),
220 which facilitates the bypass of replication-blocking lesions (see below). In fission yeast, however,
221 these modifications are observed during S phase even in the absence of exogenous DNA-damaging
222 agents (Frampton et al., 2006). Similarly, PCNA monoubiquitylation has been detected during
223 replication of undamaged DNA in *X. laevis* egg extracts and was found to be required for efficient
224 chromosomal replication (Leach and Michael, 2005). It is currently unclear, however, whether PCNA
225 ubiquitylation contributes to the normal replication process itself or rather reflects higher levels of
226 endogenous damage or fork problems in these systems.

227 **2.4 Modification of DNA polymerases**

228 All replicative DNA polymerases have been identified as ubiquitin and/or SUMO targets in budding
229 yeast and mammalian cells (Wagner et al., 2011;Cremona et al., 2012). Mammalian DNA
230 polymerase δ , responsible mainly for lagging strand synthesis, consists of four subunits (Hubscher et
231 al., 2002), two of which, p12 and p66, are ubiquitylated during a normal S phase without leading to
232 proteasomal degradation (Liu and Warbrick, 2006). Additionally, p66 is modified by SUMO at two
233 different residues, K258 and K433 (Liu and Warbrick, 2006). Although the biological significance of
234 these modifications remains unclear, it has been proposed that they might regulate protein-protein
235 interactions within the polymerase complex or with other replication factors (Liu and Warbrick,
236 2006). A study in *Schizosaccharomyces pombe* showed that the catalytic subunit of the leading strand
237 polymerase ϵ , Pol2, is polyubiquitylated and undergoes significant proteasome-dependent
238 degradation during unperturbed S phase, involving the ubiquitin ligase SCF^{PoB} (the homolog of
239 budding yeast SCF^{Dia2}) (Roseaulin et al., 2013). In contrast, Pol3, the catalytic subunit of polymerase
240 δ , remained stable despite being ubiquitylated. The authors propose that the high rate of Pol2
241 turnover might ensure a continuous supply of “fresh” polymerase at the leading strand, while the
242 discontinuous nature of lagging strand synthesis would not require an active exchange mechanism
243 (Roseaulin et al., 2013). It will be interesting to address whether polymerase ϵ degradation serves a
244 regulatory or a quality control purpose, and whether the phenomenon is conserved in other
245 organisms.

246 **2.5 Modification of Mcm10**

247 The essential, conserved minichromosome maintenance protein 10 (Mcm10) facilitates initiation of
248 DNA replication. The protein is loaded onto replication origins at the G1/S transition, where it
249 promotes strand separation either by activating the helicase or by stabilizing the formation of ssDNA,
250 but it is dispensable for assembly of the helicase itself (Kanke et al., 2012;van Deursen et al.,
251 2012;Thu and Bielinsky, 2013). A contribution of Mcm10 to the elongation step of DNA replication
252 remains controversial (Thu and Bielinsky, 2013). Mcm10 has been shown to interact with the
253 catalytic subunit of DNA polymerase α (Pol1) and regulate its stability, suggesting a role of Mcm10

254 in lagging strand synthesis (Ricke and Bielinsky, 2004). Bielinsky and colleagues reported that a
255 small fraction of Mcm10 is monoubiquitylated at two distinct lysine residues during G1 and S phase
256 of the cell cycle (Das-Bradoo et al., 2006). The modification promotes interaction with PCNA, but
257 inhibits binding of Mcm10 to polymerase α . Moreover, mutations within Mcm10's PIP box render
258 cells unviable, suggesting that the interaction between Mcm10 and PCNA is essential (Das-Bradoo et
259 al., 2006). Based on these findings, it was speculated that ubiquitylation of Mcm10 might induce a
260 conformational change to expose its PIP box, thus allowing interaction with PCNA and release of
261 polymerase α after the priming event. This might in turn facilitate the recruitment of polymerase δ
262 and thereby Okazaki fragment extension (Das-Bradoo et al., 2006; Thu and Bielinsky, 2013).

263 **2.6 Replication termination**

264 Convergence of two replication forks leads to replication termination via disassembly of the
265 replicative helicase. This process must be tightly controlled, as the CMG complex cannot be reloaded
266 after initiation and must remain associated with the replication fork until completion of the
267 replication unit, the replicon. However, in contrast to replication initiation, the mechanism of
268 replisome disassembly is not well understood.

269 Two recent reports have helped to shed light on this reaction in budding yeast and *X. laevis* egg
270 extracts, uncovering a key role for the ubiquitin system (Figure 2) (Maric et al., 2014; Moreno et al.,
271 2014). Helicase disassembly is triggered by K48-polyubiquitylation of the helicase subunit Mcm7 by
272 a member of the SCF family of ubiquitin ligases. In budding yeast, the relevant F-box protein is Dia2
273 (Maric et al., 2014). Interestingly, SCF^{Dia2} had previously been identified as a component of the
274 replication progression complex (RPC), tethered to the Ctf4 and Mrc1 subunits via a TPR domain
275 within Dia2 (Mimura et al., 2009; Morohashi et al., 2009). SCF^{Dia2} was also proposed to mediate
276 degradation of Ctf4 and Mrc1 (Mimura et al., 2009); however, a recent study has challenged this
277 model and reported instead that SCF^{Dia2} tethering to the RPC is important for the efficient
278 ubiquitylation of Mcm7 (Maculins et al., 2015). Inhibition of replication fork progression prevents
279 Mcm7 ubiquitylation, suggesting that Mcm7 ubiquitylation is restricted to terminating replisomes
280 (Maric et al., 2014; Moreno et al., 2014). How cells distinguish these from elongating complexes to
281 avoid premature ubiquitylation and disassembly of the helicase is currently unknown. One possible
282 scenario is that ubiquitylation is triggered by a DNA-mediated signal: while during replication the
283 CMG helicase encircles ssDNA, it must enclose dsDNA upon termination (Bell, 2014). The
284 mechanism of CMG helicase disassembly is likely to be conserved in higher eukaryotes. Homologs
285 of Dia2 have yet to be identified, but other ubiquitin ligases might be involved in the process.
286 Notably, disassembly of the CMG helicase requires the ubiquitin-dependent segregase p97, also
287 called VCP (in yeast: Cdc48) (Maric et al., 2014; Moreno et al., 2014), an AAA ATPase that
288 remodels and thus extracts ubiquitylated proteins from protein complexes, membranes or chromatin,
289 in many cases presenting them for proteasomal degradation (Vaz et al., 2013) (see also chapter by
290 Hoppe). Inactivation of p97 led to the accumulation of ubiquitylated forms of CMG on the
291 chromatin, while inhibition of the proteasome did not block CMG disassembly (Maric et al.,
292 2014; Moreno et al., 2014). Thus, whether Mcm7^{Ub} is degraded after extraction remains to be seen,
293 although the K48-linkage of the polyubiquitin chain on Mcm7 would imply proteasomal action.

294 **3 Ubiquitin and SUMO in DNA replication stress**

295 Replication stress is broadly defined as a condition that interferes with replication fork progression
296 (Zeman and Cimprich, 2014). It is caused by a range of intrinsic or exogenous factors, including
297 polymerase inhibition or nucleotide depletion, imbalances in the levels of replication proteins,

298 interference from ongoing transcription, incorporation of ribonucleotides, or physical barriers to the
299 DNA polymerases, such as sequences inherently prone to form secondary structures, tightly bound
300 proteins, or DNA lesions arising from chemical alterations or strand breaks. Conditions that impair
301 the replicative DNA polymerases without impeding strand unwinding by the helicase result in an
302 accumulation of ssDNA. This in turn initiates a replication-specific checkpoint response via the
303 protein kinase ATR in order to stabilize stalled replication intermediates, suppress the firing of late
304 origins and prevent entry into mitosis (Jossen and Bermejo, 2013). Depending on the nature of the
305 blockage, ATR signaling promotes replication fork rescue or restart in one of several ways, for
306 example by means of re-priming downstream of the problematic region, fork reversal, translesion
307 synthesis or strand exchange between the sister chromatids (Jossen and Bermejo, 2013;Leman and
308 Noguchi, 2013). Prolonged replication fork stalling or lack of an appropriate checkpoint response can
309 cause replication fork collapse. This poorly defined event may include a dissociation of the replisome
310 and/or the formation of strand breaks, caused either passively or by the action of nucleases.
311 Importantly, fork collapse triggers the transition to a genuine DNA damage response, mediated by
312 the checkpoint kinase ATM, as is generally observed in response to DSBs. Over the past decade it
313 has become clear that ubiquitin and SUMO are key regulators of both the replication- and the
314 damage-associated branches of the checkpoint response (Ulrich, 2012;Jackson and Durocher, 2013).

315 **3.1 Proteomic analyses of the DNA replication stress response**

316 A number of large-scale proteomic studies and systematic analyses of chromatin-associated factors
317 have illustrated the dynamics of ubiquitylation and SUMOylation specifically in response to
318 replication stress (Povlsen et al., 2012;Bursomanno et al., 2015;Xiao et al., 2015). According to those
319 studies, when replication forks encounter DNA lesions, a plethora of SUMO and ubiquitin
320 modifications on multiple factors is upregulated to either protect replication forks or initiate DNA
321 repair mechanisms. In many cases, their consequences are mechanistically and functionally not well
322 characterized, and it is clear today that modification of entire protein groups is sometimes more
323 important than ubiquitylation or SUMOylation of individual factors (Psakhye and Jentsch, 2012).
324 Moreover, a clear distinction between replication stress triggered by fork stalling and a full-blown
325 damage response that might result from subsequent fork collapse has not always been attempted.

326 **3.2 Control of homologous recombination during DNA replication**

327 Homologous recombination (HR) serves as a means to repair DNA DSBs, to promote exchange of
328 genetic material and proper chromosome segregation during meiotic cell divisions, and to rescue
329 stalled or collapsed replication forks (Krejci et al., 2012). The process is initiated by strand breaks or
330 – in particular at stalled replication forks – regions of ssDNA, tightly bound by the Replication
331 Protein A (RPA) complex. RPA is exchanged for the recombination factor Rad51. In yeast, this step
332 is promoted by the RAD52 protein. In human cells, the exchange is mainly mediated by BRCA2
333 (Jensen et al., 2010;Liu et al., 2010a;Thorslund et al., 2010). The RAD51-ssDNA filament invades
334 dsDNA, forming a so-called D-loop, and exchange of genetic material proceeds via a combination of
335 DNA synthesis, branch migration and resolution or dissolution of recombination intermediates by the
336 action of nucleases. Numerous auxiliary factors, among them DNA helicases and DNA-dependent
337 ATPases, modulate HR activity either positively or negatively at every step (Krejci et al., 2012), and
338 many of them are modulated in their activities by ubiquitin and/or SUMO.

339 **3.2.1 RPA**

340 Replication protein A (RPA) is a ssDNA-binding protein complex with a central role as a scaffold in
 341 virtually all DNA transactions. In eukaryotes, RPA consists of three subunits: RPA1, RPA2 and
 342 RPA3 (Zou et al., 2006). In mammals, the largest subunit, RPA1, is stably associated with the
 343 Sentrin/SUMO-specific protease SENP6 during S-phase, which keeps RPA1 in a hypoSUMOylated
 344 state (Dou et al., 2010) (Figure 3A). In response to replication-mediated or radiation-induced DSBs,
 345 SENP6 dissociates, resulting in modification of RPA1 with SUMO2/3 through the action of unknown
 346 SUMO ligases. Two lysine residues were identified as SUMO acceptor sites: K449 was modified by
 347 a poly-SUMO chain, whereas K577 was mono-SUMOylated. Importantly, treatment with
 348 hydroxyurea (HU) or UV irradiation, which stalls replication forks without causing DSBs, did not
 349 alter the association between SENP6 and RPA1. SUMOylation of RPA enhanced its interaction with
 350 RAD51 *in vitro* and promoted HR *in vivo* (Figure 3A). Taken together, RPA1^{SUMO} seems to facilitate
 351 recruitment of RAD51 to collapsed forks and DSBs, thereby initiating HR (Dou et al., 2010).
 352 Interestingly, RAD51 contains a SIM motif that is necessary for its accumulation at damage sites
 353 (Shima et al., 2013). However, whether RPA1^{SUMO} is indeed the *in vivo* target of this SIM relevant
 354 for recruitment of RAD51 to damage sites needs to be demonstrated, considering that SUMOylation
 355 of other proteins might act synergistically or redundantly in the assembly of repair complexes
 356 (Psakhye and Jentsch, 2012). The yeast homologue of RPA1, Rfa1, is also modified by SUMO upon
 357 treatment with the alkylating agent methyl-methanesulfonate (MMS) (Burgess et al., 2007; Cremona
 358 et al., 2012), although the functional significance of this modification remains unclear.

359 More recently, Jackson and colleagues posited a plausible mechanism for the transition from RPA to
 360 RAD51 on ssDNA, relying on the SUMO-targeted ubiquitin ligase (STUbL) RNF4 (Galanty et al.,
 361 2012): in RNF4-depleted cells RAD51 fails to accumulate and RPA persists at lesions. A
 362 SUMOylation-defective RPA1 mutant exhibited a similar behavior. Based on these findings, RNF4
 363 was proposed to target RPA1^{SUMO} for proteasomal degradation (Figure 3A). Consistent with this
 364 model, RNF4 and RPA1 coimmunoprecipitated in a manner dependent on the SIM region of RNF4,
 365 suggesting that RNF4 directly recognizes RPA1^{SUMO} as a ubiquitylation target. As a consequence,
 366 RPA1 accumulates in RNF4-depleted cells after exposure to DNA damage, and several proteasome
 367 subunits become detectable at damage sites in an RNF4-dependent manner. Thus, RNF4-mediated
 368 RPA1 turnover might promote the exchange of RPA1 for RAD51 on ssDNA, stimulating HR
 369 (Galanty et al., 2012). This mechanism and the recruitment of RAD51 through RPA^{SUMO} are not
 370 mutually exclusive, as both could cooperate in promoting RAD51 filament formation (Figure 3A).
 371 However, the direct ubiquitylation of SUMO-modified RPA1 by RNF4 has yet to be demonstrated.

372 On the other hand, RPA is also ubiquitylated under conditions complementary to those that trigger its
 373 SUMOylation (Figure 3B). Ubiquitylation on multiple sites of all three RPA subunits was observed
 374 in response to replication fork stalling upon UV irradiation or treatment with other fork-stalling
 375 agents such as 4-nitroquinoline oxide or HU, but not after exposure to ionizing radiation (Elia et al.,
 376 2015). Thus, apparently cells respond to different types of damage in distinct ways, either
 377 ubiquitylating or SUMOylating RPA. Ubiquitylation of RPA, mediated by the E3 RFW3, does not
 378 lead to proteasomal degradation. Inhibition of the modification by RFW3 depletion or by means of
 379 a ubiquitylation-deficient RPA mutant caused defects in fork restart and persistence of γ -H2AX foci
 380 after release from prolonged HU treatment, as well as a reduction in HR in response to both fork
 381 stalling and direct induction of DSBs. These findings imply that RFW3-dependent ubiquitylation of
 382 RPA promotes fork stability and HR-mediated restart of collapsed forks upon exposure to replication
 383 stress (Elia et al., 2015). The exact mechanism by which RPA^{Ub} stimulates these effects remains
 384 elusive, even though it has been suggested that the modification may promote release of the RPA

385 complex from DNA and/or facilitate the recruitment of HR factors, similar to RPA^{SUMO} (Elia et al.,
386 2015). Whether ubiquitin and SUMO can coexist on the same RPA complex remains to be explored.
387 An independent study identified another ubiquitin ligase, PRP19, as the E3 responsible for RPA
388 ubiquitylation (Marechal et al., 2014). In this study, depletion of PRP19 was found to reduce
389 damage-induced RPA ubiquitylation and compromise the accumulation of the ATR-ATRIP
390 checkpoint complex at sites of damage. In addition, ATRIP was reported to exhibit an affinity for
391 K63-linked ubiquitin chains, suggesting that this modification on RPA might contribute to the
392 recruitment of ATR-ATRIP (Marechal et al., 2014). However, these findings have been called into
393 question by the observation of an unintentional side effect of the siRNAs used for the depletion of
394 PRP19, on exogenously expressed ubiquitin (Elia et al., 2015). Hence, an involvement of PRP19 in
395 RPA ubiquitylation needs to be reconfirmed.

396 3.2.2 BLM

397 The RecQ DNA helicase BLM plays an important role in genome maintenance by facilitating HR-
398 mediated DNA repair in various ways (Bohm and Bernstein, 2014). BLM protein levels are regulated
399 during the cell cycle, being lowest in G1 and peaking in late S-phase (Dutertre et al., 2000). BLM
400 normally resides in PML nuclear bodies but re-localizes to stalled replication forks in response to
401 DNA damage (Sengupta et al., 2003). At replication forks, BLM can exert both pro- and anti-
402 recombinogenic functions (Figure 4): it protects replication forks by suppressing the formation of
403 aberrant recombination events or, upon fork collapse, it promotes repair by HR. Posttranslational
404 modifications of BLM by ubiquitin and/or SUMO make key contributions to the regulation of these
405 processes (Bohm and Bernstein, 2014). Monoubiquitylation of BLM in the absence of DNA damage
406 appears important for its normal localization in PML nuclear bodies (Figure 4A). Following HU
407 treatment, BLM is further polyubiquitylated with K63-linked chains at K105, K225 and K259 by the
408 E3s RNF8 and RNF168. Polyubiquitylation of BLM was found to be required for its recruitment to
409 stalled replication forks, mediated via interaction with the ubiquitin-interacting motifs of the adaptor
410 protein RAP80 (Tikoo et al., 2013). Once at stalled replication forks, BLM suppresses excessive HR
411 (Tikoo et al., 2013) by dismantling RAD51-ssDNA filaments and disrupting D-loops (Bugreev et al.,
412 2007). Polyubiquitylation of BLM might also potentiate the protein's anti-recombinogenic effect.
413 However, constitutive association of BLM with chromatin, achieved by fusion with histone H2AX or
414 the FHA domain of MDC1, was sufficient to suppress the elevated levels of HR caused by depletion
415 of either RNF8 or RNF168, indicating that polyubiquitylation of BLM might function more as a
416 means to recruit rather than to activate the protein (Tikoo et al., 2013).

417 In addition to being ubiquitylated, BLM is modified by SUMO at multiple sites, preferentially at
418 K317 and K331 (Eladad et al., 2005). Expression of a SUMOylation-defective BLM mutant induces
419 an excess of γ -H2AX foci, DSBs and cell death under conditions of replication stress, such as
420 prolonged HU treatment, uncovering a role of BLM SUMOylation in protecting and/or restarting
421 replication forks (Figure 4B). Interestingly, cells unable to SUMOylate BLM also fail to recruit
422 RAD51 and to induce HR at stalled replication forks (Ouyang et al., 2009). In fact, as described for
423 RPA (Dou et al 2010), SUMOylation of the helicase enhances binding to Rad51 *in vitro* (Ouyang et
424 al., 2009). However, in contrast to its ubiquitylation, its SUMOylation was not required for the
425 trafficking of BLM itself to stalled forks (Ouyang et al., 2009). Thus, BLM SUMOylation might
426 function as a molecular switch to regulate its activity: unSUMOylated, polyubiquitylated BLM is
427 recruited to stalled replication forks, protecting them from deleterious HR, while BLM^{SUMO}
428 facilitates HR by promoting Rad51 recruitment to collapsed forks (Figure 3) (Ouyang et al., 2009).
429 Future studies will certainly provide insight into the molecular mechanism by which these
430 modifications regulate BLM function.

431 Little is known about posttranslational modifications of the BLM orthologue in budding yeast, Sgs1.
432 In the absence of Sgs1, cells accumulate Rad51-dependent cruciform structures at damaged
433 replication forks (Liberi et al., 2005). The same is observed in mutants of the SUMO-conjugating
434 enzyme, *ubc9* (Branzei et al., 2006), and interestingly, Sgs1 is indeed a target of SUMOylation,
435 suggesting the possibility that the modification might be important to prevent the accumulation of
436 aberrant recombinogenic structures during replication of damaged templates (Branzei et al., 2006).
437 However, in contrast to BLM modification, SUMOylation of Sgs1 does not seem to influence
438 recombination frequencies (Lu et al., 2010).

439 Sgs1 modifications also appear to impinge on the protein's subcellular localization (Bohm et al.,
440 2015): During S phase, Sgs1 forms nuclear foci that likely indicate spontaneous recombination
441 events, as they increase with ionizing radiation treatment. Upon replication fork stalling by
442 nucleotide depletion, the number of these foci is strongly reduced in a manner depending on the
443 STUbL Slx5/8 – suggesting that STUbL-mediated ubiquitylation contributes to removing Sgs1 from
444 stalled forks, thus possibly preventing unwanted recombination. However, as overall Sgs1 levels do
445 not decrease, the process does not appear to involve degradation of the helicase, but rather its re-
446 localization. The mechanism is likely conserved, since BLM^{SUMO} is also targeted by the mammalian
447 STUbL RNF4 (Galanty et al., 2012). Thus, SUMOylation of BLM/Sgs1 seems essential for the fine-
448 tuning of the protein's function: it facilitates HR repair at collapsed forks, but it also induces removal
449 of the protein from stalled forks, adding an additional level of regulation.

450 3.2.3 SRS2

451 A recent study by Branzei and coworkers has uncovered a new mechanism promoting local
452 recombination at sites of compromised replication in budding yeast (Urulangodi et al., 2015). As
453 described above, PCNA^{SUMO} recruits the helicase Srs2 to prevent unwanted recombination during
454 unperturbed S phase. Hence, removal of Srs2 should be critical in order to engage HR after fork
455 stalling. Urulangodi et al. identified Esc2, a protein containing two SUMO-like domains (SLDs), as a
456 new factor associated with stalled replication forks and controlling Srs2 levels. Via its SLDs, Esc2
457 interacts with the SIM of Srs2, thereby promoting interaction of Srs2 with the STUbL complex
458 Slx5/8 and subsequent degradation by the proteasome. Consistent with these findings, Srs2
459 SUMOylation is induced by DNA damage (Saponaro et al., 2010). Thus, local down-regulation of
460 Srs2 appears to enable recruitment of Rad51 and thereby H-mediated rescue of stalled forks
461 (Urulangodi et al., 2015). In addition, it has been shown *in vitro* that Srs2 SUMOylation and
462 interaction with PCNA^{SUMO} are mutually inhibitory (Kolesar et al., 2012), suggesting that Esc2 might
463 help to dismantle the association between PCNA^{SUMO} and Srs2. Upon dissociation from PCNA^{SUMO},
464 Srs2 would be free to undergo SUMOylation, which would disfavor re-association with PCNA^{SUMO}.
465 Alternatively, Esc2 might bypass the need for Srs2 SUMOylation by acting as a platform to recruit
466 Slx5/8 to its substrate via physical interaction of Esc2 with Slx5 (Urulangodi et al., 2015).

467 3.2.4 SLX4

468 The binding of a multitasking protein to either SUMO or ubiquitin can modulate its function by
469 conveying different contextual specificities. An example is provided by the scaffold protein SLX4,
470 which coordinates multiple DNA repair pathways through its ability to bind several nucleases.
471 Human SLX4 contains two ubiquitin-binding zinc finger (UBZ) domains that are essential for its role
472 in the Fanconi anemia (FA) pathway, facilitating repair of DNA interstrand crosslinks (ICLs) (see
473 below and chapter by Huang). In addition, SLX4 contains a cluster of SIMs, which recognizes
474 SUMO chains. How much this cluster contributes to the repair of ICLs is not entirely clear, as

475 expression of a SIM-defective mutant of SLX4 was able to effectively rescue the mitomycin C
476 (MMC) sensitivity of SLX4-deficient human cells (Guervilly et al., 2015;Ouyang et al., 2015),
477 whereas rescue was only partial in mouse cells (Gonzalez-Prieto et al., 2015). However, the SIM
478 cluster is exclusively required for efficient recruitment and retention of SLX4 to laser-induced DNA
479 damage sites, where it might enhance the association of SLX4 with multiple SUMOylated targets,
480 including RPA and MRN (Gonzalez-Prieto et al., 2015;Ouyang et al., 2015). Once at stalled forks,
481 SLX4 might, for instance, promote replication fork restart when associated with the endonuclease
482 MUS81 (Hanada et al., 2007).

483 Interestingly, the SIMs perform yet another, unexpected function: by interacting with SUMO-
484 charged Ubc9, they promote the SUMOylation of SLX4 itself and its binding partner, XPF. This
485 presumed SUMO ligase activity appears to be toxic under some conditions, as mild overexpression
486 of SLX4, but not mutation of the SIM or BTB domain, sensitizes cells to replication fork stalling
487 upon HU treatment and promotes DSBs. In contrast, E3 activity was found to be required to prevent
488 mitotic catastrophe at chromosome fragile sites, suggesting that promotion of DSB formation might
489 be beneficial in difficult-to-replicate regions of the genome (Guervilly et al., 2015). Additional work
490 will be needed to understand how the SUMO ligase activity of SLX4 contributes to genome stability
491 and whether it can target other substrates besides SLX4 and XPF.

492 **3.2.5 Smc5/6**

493 The structural maintenance of chromosomes 5 and 6 (Smc5/6) complex (Figure 5) belongs to a
494 family of multisubunit ATPases that also includes cohesion and condensin. The complex consists of
495 eight subunits, Smc5, Smc6 and six non-Smc element (Nse) subunits, Nse1– 6 (Murray and Carr,
496 2008). Smc5 and Smc6 adopt extended coiled-coil structures with globular heads at the C- and N-
497 termini that form an ATPase domain. It is believed that Smc5/6, like the related cohesin and
498 condensin complexes, is able to embrace DNA double-strands and thereby influence higher
499 chromatin organization. Consistent with this idea, Smc5/6 has been shown to sequester sister
500 chromatid intertwinings and assist replication fork rotation to relieve super-helical tension generated
501 as DNA unwinds ahead of the fork (Kegel et al., 2011).

502 In most organisms, all subunits of the Smc5/6 complex are essential for cell survival. Hypomorphic
503 mutants of Smc5/6 show mark sensitivity to perturbation of replication such as reduced dNTP levels
504 and DNA damage (Murray and Carr, 2008;Stephan et al., 2011). Moreover, Smc5/6 localizes to
505 natural replication pausing sites such as rDNA, centromeres and telomeres, and to collapsed forks
506 (Ampatzidou et al., 2006;Lindroos et al., 2006;Menolfi et al., 2015). It has been shown that HR
507 intermediates such as X-shaped molecules accumulate in Smc5/6 mutants in the course of replication
508 in yeast. This leads to lethality in mitosis due to failure of these mutants to properly segregate their
509 chromosomes (Ampatzidou et al., 2006;Branzei et al., 2006;Chen et al., 2009;Irmisch et al.,
510 2009;Bermudez-Lopez et al., 2010;Choi et al., 2010). Interestingly, restricting Smc5/6-activity to G2,
511 i.e. after completion of genome replication, is compatible with survival (Bermudez-Lopez et al.,
512 2010;Menolfi et al., 2015). These data suggest that Smc5/6 is important for resolving recombination
513 structures formed during DNA replication.

514 One of the Smc5/6 subunits, Nse2, also known as Mms21, is known to be a SUMO ligase (Andrews
515 et al., 2005;Potts and Yu, 2005;Zhao and Blobel, 2005), whereas Nse1 was proposed and
516 subsequently shown to harbor ubiquitin ligase activity (Pebernard et al., 2008;Doyle et al., 2010).

517 **3.2.5.1 Nse2/Mms21, a SUMO ligase associated with the Smc5/6 complex**

518 Nse2 associates with the coiled-coil domain of Smc5 via an essential N-terminal domain. In contrast,
 519 its C-terminal SUMO E3 domain is dispensable for survival, but important for resistance to DNA
 520 damage (McDonald et al., 2003;Andrews et al., 2005;Potts and Yu, 2005;Zhao and Blobel,
 521 2005;Duan et al., 2009). Cells lacking the Nse2 SUMO E3 activity accumulate recombination
 522 intermediates following DNA replication stress, similar to *smc5/6* hypomorphic mutants (Branzei et
 523 al., 2006;Chavez et al., 2010). This suggests that the Smc5/6 complex responds to DNA damage
 524 primarily through its associated SUMOylation activity.

525 A recent study has provided new insight into the activation mechanism of Nse2's SUMO E3 activity
 526 towards its mostly chromatin-bound targets. Torres-Rosell and colleagues reported that ATP binding
 527 by the globular head of Smc5 induces a conformational change in the coiled-coil region, which was
 528 found to enhance E3 activity of Nse2 (Bermudez-Lopez et al., 2015). This mechanism appears to
 529 couple the loading of Smc5/6 onto chromatin to the activation of its enzymatic activity and suggests
 530 that the Smc5/6 complex as a whole behaves like a giant SUMO E3. In contrast to the SUMO ligases
 531 of the PIAS family, Nse2 lacks a DNA-binding domain (Jackson, 2001;Ulrich, 2014). Therefore,
 532 loading of the entire Smc5/6 complex is likely required for selecting chromatin-associated substrates.
 533 In fact, many of Nse2's targets have been found to co-localize with Smc5/6 or with its associated
 534 repair sites. Not surprisingly, Nse2 SUMOylates several subunits within the Smc5/6 complex, such
 535 as Smc5, Smc6, Nse3 and Nse2 itself (Andrews et al., 2005;Potts and Yu, 2005;Zhao and Blobel,
 536 2005). Interestingly, SUMOylation by the Smc5/6 complex impinges on the structurally related
 537 cohesin complex: in response to DNA damage Nse2 SUMOylates all cohesin subunits, Smc1, Smc3
 538 and Scc1. The modification is required for proper loading of the cohesin complex under these
 539 conditions. Abolishing SUMOylation of cohesin by point mutations or by tethering a SUMO-specific
 540 isopeptidase to the complex caused defects in the establishment of sister chromatid cohesion and
 541 impaired cellular survival (Almedawar et al., 2012;Wu et al., 2012). Other substrates include DNA
 542 repair factors such as Ku70 and TRAX (Potts and Yu, 2005;Zhao and Blobel, 2005). In human cells,
 543 the complex modifies telomere-binding proteins like RAP1, TRF1 and TRF2 (Potts and Yu, 2007).
 544 In budding yeast, rDNA-associated proteins such as RNA polymerase I, Fob1 and Tof2, and the
 545 replication factors Pol2 and Mcm6 have been identified as substrates (Albuquerque et al., 2013;Hang
 546 et al., 2015). The functional consequences of these SUMOylation events are yet to be clarified.

547 **3.2.5.2 Nse1, an Smc5/6 subunit with ubiquitin ligase activity**

548 The Nse1 subunit of the Smc5/6 complex, a RING finger protein, exhibits weak ubiquitin ligase
 549 activity on its own (Pebernard et al., 2008). This activity is significantly enhanced in the presence of
 550 its direct interaction partner, Nse3. In collaboration with the E2 Ubc13/Mms2, Nse1/3 is capable of
 551 assembling K63-linked ubiquitin chains (Doyle et al., 2010). In *S. pombe*, the RING-like motif of
 552 Nse1 is not essential, but inactivation of the domain leads to hypersensitivity towards genotoxic
 553 stress (Pebernard et al., 2008). Recently, Nse3 was found to harbor DNA binding activity, and
 554 mutations in the relevant domain caused damage sensitivity and chromosome aberrations (Zabradý et
 555 al., 2015). These data indicate that Nse1/3 contribute to the activity of the Smc5/6 complex in
 556 chromosome maintenance upon genotoxic stress. However, the targets of such ubiquitin ligase
 557 activity have not been identified.

558 **3.3 DNA damage bypass**

559 DNA damage bypass, also called DNA damage tolerance, is important in situations where fork
 560 stalling has been triggered by lesions in the replication template that cannot be copied by the

561 replicative DNA polymerases (Saugar et al., 2014). Such lesions mostly represent damage that is
562 subject to base or nucleotide excision repair, i.e. small or bulky adducts, oxidative lesions, abasic
563 sites and UV-induced pyrimidine dimers. In order to prevent a permanent replication arrest, damage
564 bypass ensures complete duplication of the affected region without actually removing the lesion, and
565 excision-based repair can act subsequently when the DNA has regained its double-stranded form.
566 Two major pathways of damage bypass can be distinguished, which differ significantly in their
567 overall accuracy: on the one hand, specialized damage-tolerant DNA polymerases can copy damaged
568 DNA in a process named translesion synthesis (TLS). Due to the low fidelity of the enzymes
569 involved, this pathway, described in detail elsewhere in this volume (see chapter by Sabbioneda), is a
570 major cause of damage-induced mutagenesis. On the other hand, error-free damage bypass can be
571 accomplished by means of a so-called template switching (TS) pathway, which altogether avoids the
572 use of the damaged DNA as a replication template and instead relies on the (undamaged) sister
573 chromatid to provide accurate sequence information. This process involves recombination factors and
574 joint molecules as intermediates (Giannattasio et al., 2014), but appears to be distinct from the
575 classical HR mechanism used for DSB repair. Both branches of damage bypass can act in a
576 postreplicative manner; thus, they are not necessarily coupled to replication fork progression
577 (Daigaku et al., 2010; Karras and Jentsch, 2010).

578 3.3.1 Mono- and polyubiquitylation of PCNA

579 The profound impact of damage bypass on replication efficiency and fidelity is reflected by an
580 intricate regulation of the pathway in cells (Ulrich, 2009; McIntyre and Woodgate, 2015). Central to
581 its activation is the ubiquitylation of PCNA on a conserved lysine residue, K164 (Figure 1B).
582 Whereas monoubiquitylation by the E2-E3 pair Rad6-Rad18 promotes TLS, extension of the
583 modification to a K63-linked polyubiquitin chain by the heterodimeric E2 Ubc13-Mms2 triggers
584 error-free TS (Hoegge et al., 2002; Stelter and Ulrich, 2003). The cognate E3 in budding yeast is the
585 RING finger protein Rad5; its human homologs are HLTf and SHPRH (Motegi et al., 2008). Rad18,
586 which is rate-limiting for both TLS and TS, is recruited by RPA-covered ssDNA through physical
587 interactions with the RPA complex (Davies et al., 2008; Niimi et al., 2008). In budding yeast,
588 damage-independent SUMOylation of PCNA (see above) provides a second signal that strongly
589 stimulates Rad18's activity towards PCNA (Parker and Ulrich, 2012). Additional E3s have been
590 reported to operate on mammalian PCNA, such as RNF8 and CRL4^{Cdt2} (Simpson et al., 2006; Zhang
591 et al., 2008; Teraï et al., 2010; Krijger et al., 2011). Moreover, large-scale mass spectrometry studies
592 have identified multiple other ubiquitylation sites (McIntyre and Woodgate, 2015). However, the
593 relevance of these conjugation factors and modifications for damage bypass is still a matter of debate,
594 and links to proteasomal degradation may not be excluded (Yu et al., 2009; Cazzalini et al., 2014).

595 Activation of TLS by monoubiquitylated PCNA can largely be explained by the presence of
596 ubiquitin-binding domains within the major family of damage-tolerant polymerases, which convey an
597 enhanced affinity for the modified form of PCNA (Watanabe et al., 2004; Bienko et al., 2005; Bi et al.,
598 2006; Plosky et al., 2006). In mammals, direct interactions with Rad18 also contribute to the
599 recruitment of TLS polymerases (Watanabe et al., 2004). Whereas in yeast TLS-mediated damage-
600 induced mutagenesis nearly completely depends on PCNA ubiquitylation, the process appears to be
601 less dependent on this modification in vertebrate cells (Stelter and Ulrich, 2003; Edmunds et al.,
602 2008; Hendel et al., 2011). In addition to the damage-tolerant polymerases, a number of auxiliary
603 factors have been proposed to modulate TLS via recognition of monoubiquitylated PCNA in
604 mammals. These include the UBZ domain-containing proteins SNM1A, a nuclease that might
605 provide a link between TLS and the repair of interstrand crosslinks, and DVC1 (also called Spartan),
606 an adaptor for the ubiquitin-dependent chaperone p97 (Yang et al., 2010; Centore et al., 2012). The

607 selectivity of DVC1's UBZ domain for PCNA^{Ub} has been contested, however, and it has been
608 proposed that the protein binds to other ubiquitylated proteins at sites of replication stalling, where it
609 would mediate extraction of polymerase η in order to limit TLS activity (Davis et al., 2012; Mosbech
610 et al., 2012). Downregulation of TLS appears to be important for preventing excessive mutagenesis
611 during replication. In human cells, this is accomplished mainly by PCNA deubiquitylation via the
612 isopeptidase USP1 (Huang et al., 2006). In addition, the ubiquitin-like modifier ISG15 was recently
613 found to contribute to the termination of TLS by modification of PCNA, which in turn mediated the
614 recruitment of USP10 for PCNA deubiquitylation and dissociation of polymerase η (Park et al.,
615 2014). Intriguingly, a viral isopeptidase, BPLF1, was also shown to deubiquitylate human PCNA
616 during replication of the Epstein-Barr genome, thus inhibiting polymerase η recruitment during the
617 lytic phase of infection (Whitehurst et al., 2012). How an inhibition of TLS may promote viral
618 replication is not yet understood. In yeast, PCNA deubiquitylation is mediated by Ubp10; however,
619 despite an accumulation of PCNA^{Ub}, inactivation of the enzyme does not cause a noticeable increase
620 in mutation rates, indicating that reversal of the modification may be less critical for damage bypass
621 in this organism (Gallego-Sanchez et al., 2012).

622 How polyubiquitylation of PCNA triggers TS is still an unresolved question. From experiments using
623 linear head-to-tail fusions of ubiquitin moieties as mimics of polyubiquitin chains it was inferred that
624 the K63-linkage itself is important for TS activity (Zhao and Ulrich, 2010). Although putative
625 effectors that preferentially interact with polyubiquitylated PCNA have been identified, they are
626 unlikely to be directly responsible for activating TS: the human ATPase WRNIP1 and its yeast
627 homolog Mgs1 accumulate at stalled replication intermediates in a manner that depends on their UBZ
628 domain as well as PCNA ubiquitylation (Crosetto et al., 2008; Saugar et al., 2012). However, even
629 though a subset of the phenotypes of *mgs1* mutants is consistent with a function downstream of
630 PCNA^{Ub} (Hishida et al., 2006; Saugar et al., 2012), no obvious TS defects are observed in such
631 mutants. In human cells, WRNIP1 appears to contribute to checkpoint activation as a bridging factor
632 that promotes interaction of PCNA^{Ub} with the ATM-associated ATMIN protein (Kanu et al., 2015).
633 Yet, this function is unlikely to be related to polyubiquitylation, as a single ubiquitin moiety is
634 sufficient to stimulate the interaction between WRNIP1/Mgs1 with PCNA (Saugar et al., 2012). A
635 second ATPase, ZRANB3, has also been implicated in PCNA-dependent damage bypass, based on
636 its localization to laser-induced DNA damage, its preferential interaction with polyubiquitylated
637 PCNA, and a general sensitivity to replication stress upon depletion of the protein (Ciccia et al.,
638 2012; Weston et al., 2012). However, a function in the TS pathway has yet to be properly established
639 by means of genetic analysis. Moreover, a convincing yeast homolog has not been identified, which
640 argues for an auxiliary function of ZRANB3 rather than a key role in activating TS.

641 Analysis of the TS pathway is further complicated by the multi-functionality of Rad5 and its two
642 human homologs, whose catalytic RING domains are embedded in SWI/SNF-like domains with
643 helicase and DNA-dependent ATPase activity. Although this helicase function can be genetically
644 separated from Rad5's role in ubiquitin-dependent TS, it does contribute to survival of replication
645 stress (Choi et al., 2015). Interestingly, Rad5 and its homologs have been implicated not only in TS,
646 but also in TLS in budding and fission yeast as well as humans (Minesinger and Jinks-Robertson,
647 2005; Gangavarapu et al., 2006; Pages et al., 2008; Coulon et al., 2010; Lin et al., 2011; Kuang et al.,
648 2013). Mechanistically, this activity remains controversial, as some studies have invoked PCNA
649 polyubiquitylation in the process, whereas others have reported a RING- and ATPase-independent
650 function or a dependence on a physical interaction with the TLS polymerase Rev1. Moreover,
651 although both HLTF and SHPRH are capable of polyubiquitylating PCNA *in vitro*, they have been
652 postulated to fulfill non-redundant functions in cooperation with TLS polymerases η and κ ,

653 respectively, depending on the nature of the damaging agent (Lin et al., 2011). Based on these
654 observations, Cimprich and coworkers have put forth a model where a damage-tolerant polymerase
655 harboring multiple UBDs, such as polymerase κ , might preferentially recognize polyubiquitylated
656 PCNA, while monoubiquitylation might stimulate those polymerases with only one UBD, such as
657 polymerase η . Along similar lines, Fuchs and coworkers proposed that polyubiquitylated PCNA
658 might serve to simultaneously attract several different TLS polymerases for cooperation in damage
659 bypass (Coulon et al., 2010). In contrast, observations by Zhuang and coworkers in an *in vitro* set-up
660 have led to the opposite conclusion: rather than promoting TLS, polyubiquitylation of PCNA was
661 found to inhibit the activity of polymerase η in the bypass of an abasic site, suggesting that the K63-
662 chains trap the polymerase in a non-productive mode (Yang et al., 2014). In budding yeast, genetic
663 analysis supports a positive effect of Rad5 on TLS in some situations. At the same time, however,
664 PCNA polyubiquitylation promotes damage resistance even in the absence of any damage-tolerant
665 polymerase, thus clearly implying a TLS-independent function in TS (Zhao and Ulrich, 2010). In
666 summary, the consequences of PCNA polyubiquitylation remain to be elucidated in molecular terms,
667 and future studies will be needed in order to gain insight into how the balance between mutagenic
668 TLS and error-free TS is controlled *in vivo*.

669 3.3.2 Ubiquitylation of other damage bypass factors

670 Besides PCNA, numerous other factors involved in DNA damage bypass have been identified as
671 ubiquitylation and/or SUMOylation targets (McIntyre and Woodgate, 2015). As many of the
672 modifications were detected in the context of large-scale proteomics screens, their relevance for
673 damage bypass has not always been confirmed. Nevertheless, some common patterns indicate
674 potential regulatory impacts. For example, all human TLS polymerases of the Y-family are
675 ubiquitylated, and in many cases this depends on their own ubiquitin-binding domains. Although this
676 is reminiscent of the E3-independent phenomenon of coupled ubiquitylation (Hoeller et al., 2007),
677 relevant ubiquitin ligases have actually been identified, such as Pirh2, Mdm2 and TRIP in the case of
678 polymerase η (Jung et al., 2010; Jung et al., 2011; Jung et al., 2012; Wallace et al., 2014). While Pirh2
679 attaches monoubiquitin, which apparently inhibits TLS by preventing interaction of the polymerase
680 with PCNA^{Ub} (Bienko et al., 2010), Mdm2 achieves the same effect by targeting polymerase η for
681 polyubiquitylation and proteasomal degradation. In contrast, polyubiquitylation by the TRAF-
682 interacting protein TRIP was reported to promote polymerase η localization to nuclear foci. The
683 *Drosophila melanogaster* homolog of TRIP, NOPO, is known to assemble K63-linked chains,
684 possibly indicating a regulatory function of TRIP-mediated polymerase η modification as well, and
685 interactions of both TRIP and NOPO with several Y-family polymerases suggest a conservation of
686 the process (Wallace et al., 2014). In budding yeast, polymerase η has been found to be ubiquitylated
687 as well; however, the effects of this modification on protein stability remain controversial (Parker et
688 al., 2007; Skoneczna et al., 2007; Pabla et al., 2008; Plachta et al., 2015). Ubiquitin-mediated
689 proteolysis also controls the levels of budding yeast TLS polymerase Rev1 along the cell cycle, thus
690 limiting the bulk of its mutagenic activity to the G2/M phase (Waters and Walker, 2006). Finally,
691 Woodgate and coworkers showed that ubiquitylation of human Y-family polymerases appears to
692 promote mutual interactions via their ubiquitin-binding domains and – as a consequence – facilitate
693 their cooperation in TLS (McIntyre et al., 2013).

694 Another recurring theme in the regulation of damage bypass is the protection of critical factors from
695 proteolysis. This may be achieved by the SUMOylation of a protein, as is observed in the nematode
696 *C. elegans*, where SUMOylation of polymerase η and potentially κ prevents their ubiquitin-mediated
697 degradation during early embryonic development (Kim and Michael, 2008; Roerink et al., 2012).

698 Alternatively, deubiquitylation can effectively stabilize a chromatin-associated protein by preventing
699 its extraction or proteasomal degradation. In human cells, the isopeptidase USP7 appears to play a
700 major role in this manner. As described above, its activity is important even during unperturbed
701 replication (Lecona et al., 2016). In response to replication stress, USP7 deubiquitylates a number of
702 different proteins, among them polymerase η , Mdm2, Rad18 and HLTF. By acting on polymerase η
703 and Mdm2, USP7 directly and indirectly stabilizes the polymerase and thereby facilitates TLS (Qian
704 et al., 2015). Deubiquitylation of Rad18 and HLTF was also observed to stabilize the E3s and thus
705 contribute positively to PCNA mono- and polyubiquitylation, respectively (Qing et al.,
706 2011; Zlatanou et al., 2016). In addition, Cimprich and coworkers reported that a failure to
707 deubiquitylate Rad18 prevented its efficient recruitment and interaction with SHPRH, thus promoting
708 mutagenic TLS at the expense of error-free TS (Zeman et al., 2014). Surprisingly, USP7 also
709 deubiquitylates PCNA (Kashiwaba et al., 2015). However, unlike the S phase-associated activity of
710 USP1, USP7 activity towards PCNA was not found to be coupled to replication and was therefore
711 proposed to prevent damage-induced mutagenesis during cell cycle-independent processes such as
712 other DNA repair events. In summary, USP7 appears to be an important modulator of replication
713 efficiency and fidelity not only during unperturbed replication, but also during DNA damage bypass.

714 3.4 The Fanconi Anemia pathway

715 DNA interstrand cross-links (ICLs) are strongly replication fork-stalling lesions that are not only
716 refractory to copying by replicative DNA polymerases, but also prevent strand separation and
717 passage of the helicase. Accordingly, their processing in replicating cells requires an intricate
718 operation involving components of several repair pathways, namely TLS polymerases, HR proteins
719 and structure-specific nucleases. In vertebrate cells, cooperation between these factors is mediated by
720 the Fanconi anemia (FA) pathway, named after a rare hereditary disease associated with bone-
721 marrow failure, congenital abnormalities, cancer predisposition and a marked sensitivity to ICL-
722 causing agents (Kottemann and Smogorzewska, 2013; Walden and Deans, 2014). Sixteen genes have
723 been assigned to this pathway by means of epistasis analysis, and half of these encode subunits of a
724 multimeric ubiquitin ligase, the FA core complex (see chapter by Huang). This E3 is recruited to
725 chromatin upon stalling of the replisome upstream of an ICL, where its catalytic subunit, FANCL,
726 monoubiquitylates a heterodimer of two other FA proteins, FANCD2 and FANCI (Alpi et al.,
727 2008; Longerich et al., 2009; Sato et al., 2012). The ubiquitylated form of this “ID complex” initiates
728 ICL processing, which involves the generation of a collapsed fork as a step towards the unhooking of
729 the cross-link by dual incisions on either side of the lesion. It is followed by TLS-mediated repair
730 synthesis and HR-mediated reactivation of the replication fork. How these downstream events are
731 accomplished has only recently been elucidated. Central to the unhooking step is the scaffold protein,
732 SLX4/FANCP, which recognizes the ubiquitylated ID complex by means of two ubiquitin-binding
733 UBZ domains and interacts with a number of structure-specific nucleases that mediate the actual
734 incisions (Zhang and Walter, 2014). Ubiquitin binding by SLX4 is required for cellular resistance
735 specifically towards DNA cross-linking agents (Kim et al., 2013), and mutations in SLX4 confer a
736 FA phenotype in humans, highlighting the importance of SLX4 for ICL repair (Kim et al.,
737 2011; Stoepker et al., 2011).

738 Another structure-specific endonuclease, FANCD2/FANCI-associated nuclease 1 (FAN1), was
739 identified to act downstream of the ID complex (Kratz et al., 2010; Liu et al., 2010b; MacKay et al.,
740 2010; Smogorzewska et al., 2010). Like SLX4, FAN1 carries a UBZ domain that was reported to
741 mediate the recruitment to damage sites via binding to monoubiquitylated FANCD2. However,
742 FAN1 was found to be dispensable for ICL incision in a cell-free system (Klein Douwel et al., 2014).

743 Moreover, patients carrying a *FAN1* homozygous microdeletion do not suffer from typical FA
744 conditions (Trujillo et al., 2012), thus arguing against a contribution of the nuclease to the FA
745 pathway. Insight into this conundrum has very recently come from the observation that FAN1 instead
746 prevents genomic instability induced by replication fork stalling events unrelated to ICLs (Lachaud et
747 al., 2016). Thus, ubiquitylation of the ID complex by the FA core complex appears to serve a two-
748 fold purpose in response to replication stress, depending on the downstream effectors: a highly
749 specialized ICL repair pathway triggered by SLX4 recruitment, and an independent, more general
750 fork protection mechanism by means of FAN1.

751 Interestingly, the FA pathway appears to be intimately connected with another system for replication
752 fork protection, the Rad18- and PCNA-dependent damage bypass mechanism described above. Not
753 only does ICL processing require the activity of TLS polymerases, but the central initiating event of
754 the FA pathway, the activation of the ID complex, was actually found to depend on Rad18, the E3
755 responsible for PCNA monoubiquitylation. The exact relationship between the two pathways is still a
756 matter of controversy, as one study observed an interaction between FANCL and PCNA^{Ub} that was
757 required for efficient recruitment of FANCL to chromatin (Geng et al., 2010), whereas another report
758 postulated a direct role of Rad18 in binding and recruitment of FANCD2 in a manner independent of
759 PCNA modification (Williams et al., 2011). Another piece of evidence for a tight coordination
760 between the two pathways is the notion that the isopeptidase USP1 mediates deubiquitylation of both
761 PCNA and the ID complex (Nijman et al., 2005;Huang et al., 2006). Controlling the ubiquitylation of
762 these two key players appears to be essential for proper replication fork maintenance, as loss of USP1
763 causes high levels of genome instability and mutagenesis (Huang et al., 2006).

764 A recent study discovered a regulatory circuit of polyubiquitin and SUMO that also appears to
765 contribute to controlling FA pathway activity at sites of replication problems (Gibbs-Seymour et al.,
766 2015): upon treatment with replication fork-stalling agents, FANCD2 and FANCI are SUMOylated
767 by two SUMO E3 ligases, PIAS1 and PIAS4, in a manner dependent on prior activation of the ID
768 complex by monoubiquitylation. The modification targets the proteins for RNF4-mediated
769 polyubiquitylation and subsequent extraction from the chromatin by the p97 segregase in complex
770 with DVC1. Hence, this mechanism may limit ID complex dosage at the sites of replication stress in
771 order to terminate the response or avoid excessive activity of the FA pathway.

772 4 Replication of chromatin

773 Genome replication occurs in the context of chromatin. Hence, for efficient copying of genomic
774 DNA, nucleosomes must be disrupted ahead of an advancing replication fork. Upon passage of the
775 fork, chromatin structure must rapidly be restored, and loss of epigenetic information in the process
776 needs to be avoided. It is therefore not surprising that many chromatin components are targets of the
777 ubiquitin and/or SUMO system for regulatory purposes, and these modifications are known to be
778 important for the replication process itself.

779 4.1 Ubiquitylation of histones H2A and H2B

780 Histone H2A was the first protein discovered to be modified by ubiquitin (Goldknopf et al., 1975). In
781 fact, H2A and H2B are two of the most abundant ubiquitylation targets in the nucleus (Cao and Yan,
782 2012). Both H2A and H2B are predominantly modified by monoubiquitin. H2B was found to be
783 monoubiquitylated at K123 in *S. cerevisiae* or K123 and 120 in human cells, which plays an
784 important role in transcriptional regulation (Henry et al., 2003;Wood et al., 2003;Kao et al.,
785 2004;Nakanishi et al., 2009;Song and Ahn, 2010). In yeast, H2B monoubiquitylation is mediated by

786 the E2 Rad6 and the E3 Bre1 (Robzyk et al., 2000; Wood et al., 2003). The mammalian homologs of
787 Bre1, RNF20 and RNF40 (Kim et al., 2005), cooperate with the E2s hRad6 and UbcH6 (Koken et al.,
788 1991). H2B^{Ub} promotes di- and tri-methylation of H3 at K4, which controls various aspects of
789 transcription (Dover et al., 2002; Sun and Allis, 2002; Krogan et al., 2003), among them a stabilization
790 of the histone chaperone complex FACT (Fleming et al., 2008).

791 Beyond its role in transcriptional regulation, H2B^{Ub} has been implicated in DNA replication (Figure
792 6A). This connection was established by the observation that Bre1 is enriched around replication
793 origins, where it contributes to maintaining H2B^{Ub} levels on newly replicated DNA (Trujillo and
794 Osley, 2012). Whereas a ubiquitylation-deficient mutant of H2B, K123R, is highly sensitive to
795 replication fork-stalling agents (Trujillo and Osley, 2012; Lin et al., 2014), H3 mutants that abolish
796 methylation are significantly less sensitive (Trujillo and Osley, 2012). This argues that the
797 contribution of H2B^{Ub} to replication is independent of its regulatory role in transcription, mediated
798 through histone methylation. In cells lacking H2B^{Ub}, despite efficient formation of the pre-RC,
799 association of replisome components such as polymerases ϵ and α and RPA with origins is impaired
800 (Trujillo and Osley, 2012), as is replication progression after HU treatment (Lin et al., 2014). Also,
801 PCNA associates normally at origins, but its levels are reduced at more distal sites, suggesting that
802 the H2B-K123R mutant does not affect origin firing, but rather fork progression under conditions of
803 replication stress (Trujillo and Osley, 2012). In addition, lack of H2B^{Ub} leads to a defect in the
804 binding of the FACT complex and reduced nucleosome occupancy in newly replicated DNA under
805 the same stress condition (Trujillo and Osley, 2012; Lin et al., 2014). H2B^{Ub}'s effect on FACT in this
806 context is reminiscent of its role during transcription. Since FACT is known to stimulate the activity
807 of the Mcm helicase (Tan et al., 2006), it was speculated that H2B^{Ub} could play a role in facilitating
808 the unwinding of DNA ahead of the fork to promote replication progression. However, this view was
809 challenged by a recent report from Kao and colleagues, who postulated that H2B^{Ub} may instead
810 function to limit uncontrolled fork progression. They observed significant elongation of replication
811 tracts in the absence of H2B^{Ub} after HU treatment, together with increased levels of H2A
812 phosphorylation, a sign of fork damage (Lin et al., 2014). In support of this model, fork progression
813 under conditions of replication stress is also strongly enhanced in *rad6* Δ cells (Yu et al., 2014).

814 Taken together, ubiquitylation of H2B appears to coordinate nucleosome assembly with fork
815 progression, an activity that becomes particularly important when the replisome is challenged by
816 replication stress such as nucleotide depletion or DNA damage. However, the precise mechanism and
817 the effectors of the modification are yet to be defined.

818 H2A is well known to be ubiquitylated at the conserved residue K119 by the polycomb repressive
819 complex 1 (PRC1), which comprises the RING-E3 subunits RING1A or RING1B and BMI1 together
820 with the E2 UbcH5c (Gao et al., 2012; McGinty et al., 2014). The mark is essential for establishing
821 repressive chromatin during development (Lanzuolo and Orlando, 2012; Di Croce and Helin, 2013).
822 However, H2A^{Ub} may also play a role in the replication of intact and damaged DNA (Figure 6B).
823 RING1B localizes to sites of replication (Lee et al., 2014; Piunti et al., 2014), and several Polycomb
824 proteins were also found to be recruited to sites of DNA damage (Bergink et al., 2006; Chou et al.,
825 2010; Ginjala et al., 2011), suggesting that H2A^{Ub} may contribute to damage signaling at replication
826 forks. In fact, loss of PRC function causes an increase in asymmetric forks, indicating perturbed
827 replication dynamics (Piunti et al., 2014; Bravo et al., 2015). Conversely, enhancement of H2A
828 ubiquitylation by depletion of the ubiquitin-specific protease USP3 in mammalian cells causes delays
829 in S phase progression and increased formation of ssDNA and DNA breaks (Nicassio et al., 2007).
830 These observations are consistent with H2A^{Ub} acting as a damage signal that – when present in

831 excess – leads to a hyperactivation of the damage response that would generate abnormal replication
832 or repair structures causing genomic instability.

833 A recent study suggests a special role of H2A^{Ub} in the replication of pericentromeric heterochromatic
834 domains, which are duplicated late in S phase (Bravo et al., 2015). Cells deficient in all RING1
835 activities were found to accumulate high levels of ssDNA in these regions, along with increased
836 spontaneous levels of γ H2AX and a delayed transition from middle to late S-phase. Consistent with
837 these findings, H2A^{Ub} colocalizes with PCNA in late S phase (Vassilev et al., 1995). Interestingly,
838 selective restoration of H2A^{Ub} within the pericentromeric heterochromatic domains by means of a
839 fusion construct of RING1B, BMI1 and methyl-CpG binding domain protein 1 (MBD1) rescued the
840 defect in S phase progression in RING1-deficient cells (Bravo et al., 2015). Given the enrichment of
841 major satellite repeats in pericentric heterochromatin and their propensity to form secondary
842 structures, the strong effect of H2A^{Ub} in these regions may well reflect a general contribution of the
843 modification to the replication of problematic sequences.

844 The mechanism by which H2A^{Ub} influences DNA replication is still unknown, but some insight
845 comes from the observation that BRCA1-associated protein-1 (BAP1) recognizes H2A^{Ub} at
846 replication forks and recruits the ATP-dependent chromatin remodeler Ino80. BAP1 deubiquitinates
847 INO80 and thereby protects the protein from ubiquitin-mediated proteolysis (Lee et al., 2014).
848 Hence, via BAP1 recruitment H2A^{Ub} might allow the INO80 complex to exert its well-known role in
849 stabilizing stalled replication forks and assisting fork restart (Papamichos-Chronakis and Peterson,
850 2008; Shimada et al., 2008; Vincent et al., 2008; Falbo et al., 2009; Vassileva et al., 2014).

851 4.2 Ubiquitylation of histone H3 in replication-coupled nucleosome assembly

852 In order to ensure proper restoration of chromatin structure upon genome replication, the nucleosome
853 assembly machinery is tightly coupled to replication fork progression. In budding yeast, this is
854 achieved by means of a pathway involving acetylation of histone H3, a marker of newly synthesized
855 histones (Figure 6C). In front of a replication fork, nucleosomes are disassembled by the action of the
856 Mcm2-7 complex and histone chaperone Asf1 (Groth et al., 2007; Huang et al., 2015). Behind the
857 fork, both parental and newly synthesized histones contribute to the restoration of chromatin
858 structure. In *S. cerevisiae*, preferential binding of Asf1 to the H3-H4 dimer stimulates acetylation of
859 newly synthesized H3 at K56 by the histone acetyltransferase Rtt109 (Masumoto et al., 2005; Driscoll
860 et al., 2007; Han et al., 2007a). H3K56^{ac} enhances binding of H3-H4 to histone chaperones Rtt106
861 and CAF-1 (Li et al., 2008). CAF-1 in turn interacts with PCNA and assists in histone deposition
862 behind the fork (Shibahara and Stillman, 1999; Moggs et al., 2000; Zhang et al., 2000). H3 acetylation
863 peaks in S phase and is removed upon completion of genome replication (Masumoto et al., 2005).
864 H3K56^{ac} is also detectable in mammalian cells, although in much lower abundance compared to
865 yeast (Garcia et al., 2007; Das et al., 2009; Tjeertes et al., 2009; Yuan et al., 2009; Jasencakova et al.,
866 2010), suggesting that either the modification is much more transient, or other acetylation sites can
867 substitute for H3K56. Defects in the Asf1-Rtt109-H3K56^{ac} pathway result in various aspects of
868 genome instability, including reduced replisome function under conditions of replication stress
869 (Franco et al., 2005; Schulz and Tyler, 2006; Han et al., 2007b; Clemente-Ruiz et al., 2011), sensitivity
870 to DNA-damaging agents (Driscoll et al., 2007; Li et al., 2008), loss of sister chromatid cohesion,
871 excessive recombination and high rates of gross chromosomal rearrangements (Myung et al.,
872 2003; Prado et al., 2004; Ramey et al., 2004; Thaminy et al., 2007; Kadyrova et al., 2013; Munoz-
873 Galvan et al., 2013).

874 Intriguingly, a large-scale genetic screen in budding yeast identified the CRL ubiquitin ligase
875 complex, Rtt101^{Mms1/Mms22}, as a downstream effector of the pathway (Collins et al., 2007b).
876 Rtt101^{Mms1} is believed to be the budding yeast ortholog of human CRL4^{DDB1} and assembles with the
877 substrate adaptor Mms22 in a DNA damage-induced manner (Zaidi et al., 2008; Han et al., 2010; Han
878 et al., 2013). Inactivation of the complex causes damage sensitivity and defects in fork progression
879 through damaged DNA and natural replication pause sites such as ribosomal DNA loci, and these
880 defects are epistatic with the lack of Rtt109 (Luke et al., 2006; Duro et al., 2008; Zaidi et al.,
881 2008; Wurtele et al., 2012). Moreover, Rtt109 was indeed found to recruit Rtt101 to chromatin
882 (Roberts et al., 2008).

883 Despite the strong genetic link between the Asf1-Rtt109-H3K56^{ac} nucleosome assembly pathway and
884 Rtt101^{Mms1/Mms22} in replisome functions and genome maintenance, their cooperation is not well
885 understood in mechanistic terms. A recent report might provide insight into the process. Zhang and
886 colleagues found that Rtt101^{Mms1/Mms22} preferentially binds H3K56^{ac}-H4 over unmodified H3-H4 and
887 can directly ubiquitylate H3 at lysine residues 121, 122 and 125 (Han et al., 2013). This in turn
888 weakens H3 interaction with Asf1 and instead facilitates association with CAF-1 for subsequent
889 deposition behind the replication fork. This function appears to be conserved in human cells, as
890 depletion of CRL4^{DDB1} results in enhanced interaction of H3-H4 with Asf1 and reduced deposition of
891 new H3 (Han et al., 2013). Hence, Rtt101^{Mms1/Mms22}-mediated ubiquitylation of H3 appears to assist
892 in a hand-off mechanism that ensures the transfer of H3-H4 from Asf1 ahead of an advancing fork to
893 other chaperones such as CAF-1 and Rtt106 behind the fork.

894 How does nucleosome assembly influence replisome stability? There is growing evidence indicating
895 that coupling of nucleosome assembly and replication progression is essential for maintenance of
896 intact replisomes. This view is supported by the observation that deregulation of histone supply
897 causes replication forks to collapse, followed by recombination-mediated rescue (Groth et al.,
898 2007; Clemente-Ruiz and Prado, 2009; Takayama and Toda, 2010; Clemente-Ruiz et al.,
899 2011; Mejlvang et al., 2014). This effect is reminiscent of the situation where lack of the Asf1-
900 Rtt109-H3K56^{ac} or Rtt101^{Mms1/Mms22} pathway causes a decoupling of nucleosome assembly and
901 replication progression.

902 Nevertheless, many mechanistic questions remain. For example, the majority of Cullin-based
903 ubiquitin ligases are known to produce K48-linked polyubiquitin chains that target their substrates
904 for proteasomal degradation (Komander and Rape, 2012; Mattioli and Sixma, 2014), and the E2
905 Cdc34 that associates with Rtt101 is also known to assemble K48-chains (Ye and Rape, 2009). Yet,
906 H3 itself is unlikely to be a substrate of the proteasome. This has led to the idea that Rtt101^{Mms1/Mms22}
907 may target other components at stalled forks for degradation in order to facilitate repair or restart.
908 Indeed, one such substrate could be the FACT complex (Han et al., 2010), which requires Rtt101
909 specifically for localization to sites of replication, but not to transcription sites. Intriguingly,
910 however, in this case a K63-linked ubiquitin chain was detected on FACT (Han et al., 2010). Hence,
911 it is still an open question whether Rtt101^{Mms1/Mms22} plays any role in proteasomal degradation
912 mediated via K48-chains.

913 4.3 Ubiquitylation of histone H3 in replication-coupled epigenetic inheritance

914 In order to maintain its identity and gene expression patterns, it is crucial for a cell to restore its
915 epigenetic information after every round of replication. Due to the semiconservative nature of DNA
916 replication, DNA is hemi-methylated after every replication cycle, and full DNA methylation has to
917 be restored in order to reestablish gene silencing. It is known that a RING-type ubiquitin ligase,

918 UHRF1 (ubiquitin-like with PHD and ring finger domains 1, also known as NP95 in mouse and
919 ICBP90 in humans), is recruited to nascent DNA after replication (Lopez-Contreras et al., 2013).
920 UHRF1 binds to hemi-methylated DNA through its SET and RING finger-associated (SRA) domain
921 (Arita et al., 2008;Avvakumov et al., 2008). Recently, Nakanishi and colleagues found that UHRF1
922 ubiquitylates histone H3 at K23 in *X. laevis* egg extracts (Nishiyama et al., 2013). Methylation is then
923 restored by DNMT1, which recognizes H3K23^{Ub} through its replication foci targeting sequence. A
924 similar mechanism is observed in mammalian cells, where UHRF1 ubiquitylates H3 at K18. Here,
925 DNMT1 binds to H3K18^{Ub} via a ubiquitin-interacting UIM motif (Qin et al., 2015). This is an
926 interesting example of how cells can use the ubiquitin system to establish other epigenetic marks
927 following DNA replication.

928 **5 Spatial regulation of ubiquitylation and SUMOylation during DNA replication**

929 The ubiquitin and SUMO systems are organized within the cell in a spatially controlled manner. One
930 important hub for the coordination of nuclear ubiquitylation and SUMOylation activities appears to
931 be the nuclear pore complex (NPC). The NPC is responsible for the transport of macromolecules
932 between the nucleus and the cytoplasm, but genetic data from budding yeast suggest that it has
933 additional functions in coordinating DNA damage signaling and repair (Figure 7). For example, it has
934 been observed that cells deficient in components of the Nup84 nuclear pore subcomplex are
935 hypersensitive to DNA-damaging agents (Bennett et al., 2001;Loeillet et al., 2005;Therizols et al.,
936 2006) and accumulate spontaneous recombination foci in S and G2 phase (Loeillet et al.,
937 2005;Palancade et al., 2007;Nagai et al., 2008). Mutations in both Nup84 and the HR pathway are
938 synthetically lethal (Loeillet et al., 2005). These findings suggest that the NPC plays a role in
939 replication during both unperturbed and stress conditions, and HR-based mechanisms to resolve fork
940 problems become essential when NPC function is compromised.

941 A number of ubiquitin- and SUMO-related enzymes are found at the nuclear pore. For instance,
942 SUMO protease Ulp1 is anchored to the nucleoporin Nup60 through myosin-like proteins (MLPs)
943 Mlp1 and Mlp2 (Zhao et al., 2004). Mutation of *ULP1* or loss of MLPs shows synthetic effects when
944 combined with mutations in HR (Zhao et al., 2004;Collins et al., 2007a;Palancade et al., 2007), and
945 deleting MLPs leads to mislocalization of Ulp1, DNA damage sensitivity and clonal lethality (Zhao
946 et al., 2004). Moreover, cells with impaired Ulp1 function accumulate ssDNA during replication
947 (Soustelle et al., 2004). It is therefore conceivable that the presence of deSUMOylating activity at the
948 nuclear pore either prevents the accumulation of toxic recombination intermediates during replication
949 or is required to resolve these structures. Proper localization of the SUMO conjugation system thus
950 impinges on the process of DNA replication itself.

951 Intriguingly, the nuclear pore is also the site of accumulation of STUbLs in yeast (Nagai et al., 2011).
952 Deletion of the STUbL complex Slx5/8 renders yeast hypersensitive to DNA-damaging agents and
953 replication stress, and the mutants show higher rates of spontaneous gross chromosomal
954 rearrangements (Zhang et al., 2006;Prudden et al., 2007;Nagai et al., 2008). Consistent with these
955 findings, collapsed replication forks – like DSBs – are redirected to the nuclear pore (Nagai et al.,
956 2008;Horigome et al., 2014). These observations prompted the hypothesis that relocalization to the
957 nuclear pore facilitates HR-mediated fork restart by means of STUbL activity, possibly via
958 degradation of SUMOylated proteins such as Srs2 (Urulangodi et al., 2015). In support of this idea,
959 Freudenreich and coworkers recently observed that sites of replication blockage created by expanded
960 CAG repeats are relocated to nuclear pores particularly in late S phase (Su et al., 2015). The authors
961 suggested that such relocalization may target Rad52^{SUMO} for degradation, which would then alter the

962 outcome of HR pathways in the context of replication restart. In humans, it has been proposed that
963 the Promyelocytic leukaemia (PML) nuclear bodies functionally resemble the yeast nuclear pores as
964 a site where the mammalian STUbL RNF4 accumulates (Nagai et al., 2011). However, it remains to
965 be tested whether perturbed replication forks are redirected to PML bodies in human cells.

966 Considering the large number of repair factors and replisome components that are SUMOylated
967 during replication (Cremona et al., 2012; Psakhye and Jentsch, 2012), directing a collapsed fork to the
968 nuclear pore may provide a window of opportunity for cells to fine-tune repair events by altering the
969 fate of various repair and replication factors via posttranslational modification. However, it is still not
970 fully understood how these activities are coordinated at the pore, for instance whether a certain factor
971 is deSUMOylated by Ulp1 or directed to proteasomal degradation through STUbL activity. How
972 such events would impact on the outcome of repair and the consequences for genome integrity awaits
973 further investigation.

974 **6 Concluding remarks**

975 The extensive range of mechanisms by which ubiquitin and SUMO impinge on eukaryotic DNA
976 replication is a very good reflection of the diversity of these two posttranslational modification
977 systems in general. Several recurring concepts, including proteasomal targeting, either by ubiquitin
978 alone or in a SUMO-dependent manner as mediated by the SUMO-targeted ubiquitin ligases, but also
979 SUMO-mediated protection from ubiquitylation and proteolysis, can be observed to operate on
980 replicating chromatin. Non-proteolytic functions, such as the enhancement of protein-protein
981 interactions via SUMOylation, monoubiquitylation or linkage-specific polyubiquitylation, play an
982 even more prominent role in the recruitment of various regulatory factors to active or stalled
983 replisomes. Importantly, when compared to replication initiation, which is largely coupled to cell
984 cycle regulatory events, replication fork progression appears to be an extremely delicate condition in
985 which numerous modulating modifications are needed to fine-tune the activity of various components
986 or stabilize weakly associated complexes in order to maintain fork integrity. No matter whether
987 individual factors or entire groups of proteins are concerned, there is a large grey area between those
988 modifications that regulate unperturbed replication and those that are initiated in response to
989 replication problems and stress conditions.

990 Perhaps not surprisingly, a few key replication factors emerge as nodes in a network of
991 posttranslational modification targets around the replication fork, such as PCNA, RPA and some
992 central recombination proteins. Complementary to these prime targets, a few conjugation and
993 deconjugation enzymes appear to dominate the replication-associated modification landscape and
994 might thus be critical for coordinating different pathways involved in signaling or damage
995 processing. These include ubiquitin ligases such as Rad18, RNF4 and the CRL4^{Cdt2} complex, but also
996 prominent isopeptidases like USP1 and USP7. Undoubtedly, the range of identified targets and
997 functions will continue to expand with the growing interest in these factors. Perhaps the biggest
998 challenge for future research will be the interpretation of the wealth of information gathered by
999 proteomics approaches. Substantiating and making sense of all the modification events that have by
1000 now been detected in system-wide screens, distinguishing relevant from bystander events, analyzing
1001 their regulation, and finally assigning a physiological role to them will occupy many laboratories for
1002 a long time to come.

1003

1004

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1009

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1837 9 Figure legends

1838 **Figure 1: Modifications of PCNA by ubiquitin and SUMO during replication of intact and**
1839 **damaged DNA. (A)** During unperturbed replication, budding yeast PCNA is SUMOylated at K164
1840 and to a minor extent at K127. Modification at K164 is mediated by SUMO E2-E3 Ubc9-Siz1.
1841 PCNA^{SUMO} recruits anti-recombinogenic helicase Srs2 to counteract Rad51 filament formation. RFC-
1842 like complex RLC-Elg1 interacts with PCNA^{SUMO} and unloads PCNA from DNA. **(B)** Upon
1843 replication stalling and exposure of ssDNA, E2-E3 complex Rad6-Rad18 is recruited by interaction
1844 with the RPA complex and (in yeast) SUMO and monoubiquitylates PCNA at K164. This
1845 modification is removed by Ubp10 (yeast) or USP1 (humans). Monoubiquitylated PCNA recruits
1846 damage-tolerant DNA polymerases for TLS, while polyubiquitylated PCNA initiates template
1847 switching by a poorly defined mechanism. Auxiliary factors DVC1 and SNM1A modulate TLS.
1848 DVC1 cooperates with the AAA ATPase p97 to extract polymerase η from chromatin.
1849 Mgs1/WRNIP1 and ZRANB3 bind to polyubiquitylated PCNA and might contribute to TS.
1850 Ubiquitylation of TLS polymerases prevents association with PCNA^{Ub} and may induce their
1851 degradation.

1852 **Figure 2: Replication termination via ubiquitin-mediated CMG helicase extraction.** A model,
1853 derived from observations in budding yeast and *X. laevis* egg extracts, proposes ubiquitylation of
1854 Mcm7 by the replisome-associated E3 SCF^{Dia2} at the sites of replication termination where two forks
1855 converge. The CMG helicase (Mcm2-7, Cdc45 and GINS) is subsequently extracted from the
1856 chromatin by Cdc48/p97 in a ubiquitin-dependent manner.

1857 **Figure 3: Ubiquitylation and SUMOylation of RPA under conditions of replicative stress. (A)**
1858 SUMOylation of RPA1 is counteracted by the protease SENP6 during unperturbed S-phase. In
1859 response to replication-mediated DSBs, SENP6 dissociates, allowing SUMOylation of RPA1 in
1860 order to facilitate HR via recruitment of RAD51. In addition, RPA^{SUMO} is recognized by the STUbL
1861 RNF4, which mediates proteasomal turnover of RPA1, thereby promoting exchange of RPA1 for
1862 RAD51. **(B)** Upon replication fork stalling, the ubiquitin E3 RFD3 ubiquitylates RPA at multiple
1863 sites, thereby promoting replication fork restart and HR repair.

1864 **Figure 4: Regulation of BLM activity under conditions of replicative stress. (A)** Upon replication
1865 fork stalling, BLM is polyubiquitylated by the ubiquitin E3s RNF8 and RNF168. Polyubiquitylated
1866 BLM is recognized by RAP80, which mediates relocation of BLM from PML nuclear bodies and
1867 recruitment to stalled forks. At the fork BLM suppresses unwanted HR events. **(B)** Upon collapse of
1868 a stalled fork, BLM is SUMOylated, thereby facilitating the recruitment of RAD51 and repair by HR.

1869 **Figure 5: Ubiquitylation and SUMOylation targets of Smc5/6 and their associated processes.**
1870 The Smc5/6 complex harbors SUMO ligase (Nse2) and ubiquitin ligase (Nse1-Nse3) subunits. DNA
1871 binding stimulates the ATPase domains at the globular heads of Smc5/6, inducing a conformational
1872 change in the coiled-coil region of Smc5 that activates the SUMO E3 activity of Nse2. Smc5/6 likely
1873 selects its ubiquitylation and/or SUMOylation targets at relevant loci where the complex is recruited.

1874 **Figure 6: Functions of histone ubiquitylation in DNA replication. (A)** Budding yeast E2-E3
1875 complex Rad6-Bre1 is recruited to sites of replication stress for H2B ubiquitylation at K123.
1876 H2BK123^{Ub} regulates fork speed and nucleosome assembly behind the fork. Via H3K9 methylation,
1877 it independently contributes to transcriptional regulation. **(B)** The Polycomb Repressive Complex
1878 (PRC) is recruited to sites of replication stress or at problematic sequences to ubiquitylate H2A at
1879 K119. H2AK119^{Ub} recruits BAP1, which maintains fork stability by protecting chromatin-
1880 remodelling INO80 complex from proteasomal degradation. **(C)** The E3 SCF^{Rtt101} ubiquitylates H3 at
1881 K121, 122 and 125. The reaction is stimulated by acetylation of H3 at K56 by histone
1882 acetyltransferase Rtt109. This facilitates transfer of the H3-H4 tetramer to CAF-1 for nucleosome
1883 deposition behind the fork. Rtt101 also ubiquitylates the chromatin reorganizing FACT complex.

1884 **Figure 7: Spatial organization of the ubiquitin and SUMO metabolism.** Both ubiquitin and
1885 SUMO conjugating and deconjugating enzymes are enriched at the Nuclear Pore Complex (NPC).
1886 Collapsed forks relocalize to NPCs, which modulates local ubiquitylation and/or SUMOylation of
1887 relevant components in order to facilitate fork restart or prevent toxic recombination events.

Figure 1

A Unperturbed DNA replication

B Replication of damaged DNA

Figure 2

Figure 3

A Replication-associated DSBs

B Replication fork stalling

Figure 4

A Replication fork stalling

B Replication fork collapse

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 7

